

COMMERCIAL BANKING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVE LEGISLATION NORMATIVE-LEGAL BASIS

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Abstract: Ensuring the stability of macroeconomic indicators in 2022-2026 will have a positive effect on the financial strength of banks. In particular, ensuring the level of inflation does not exceed 5 percent, firstly, reduces the level of decline of banks' assets in our national currency - the soum due to inflation; secondly, it creates an opportunity to reduce the interest rates of bank loans. As a result, the repayment rate of commercial banks' loans will increase and the interest income of banks will increase.

Keywords: Commercial banks, profitability of assets, income base, loans, deposits, risk, bank profit, interest expenses.

While increasing the volume of investment attraction leads to an increase in the volume of investment loans of commercial banks, the development of the country's securities market leads to an increase in the volume of commercial banks' operations with securities (asset operations, passive operations, trade-mediation operations). As a result of this, firstly, the income of commercial banks in the form of interest and dividends will increase; secondly, the ability of banks to provide current liquidity at the expense of highly liquid securities (securities of the Government and the Central Bank) will increase. The reason for this is that in the prudential requirement regarding the liquidity of the banks set by the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, investments made by commercial banks in securities of the Government and the Central Bank are considered as highly liquid assets. As a

result, investments made in securities of the Government and the Central Bank serve to increase the current liquidity of banks. [1].

Also, reducing the tax burden of business entities leads to an increase in their solvency level. As a result, their use of financial services provided by commercial banks will increase.

The strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5992 dated May 12, 2020, plays an important role. In this Strategy, "the following measures related to ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks are defined:

- gradual release of banks from assets and functions that are not specific to their activities;
- development of a national strategy for increasing the popularity of financial services;
- The minimum amount of authorized capital of banks until 2025
- 500 billion gradual increase up to soum;
- attracting independent members to supervisory boards of commercial banks with state participation;
- optimizing the growth of banks' loan portfolio and reducing the risks of loan concentration;
- development of the system of protection of population deposits;
- revising the regulatory and supervisory frameworks by introducing internationally recognized minimum standards and requirements applicable to banks;
- development and approval of regulatory legal documents taking into account the recommendations of the Basel Committee on banking supervision;
- introduction of new digital products to increase the quality and speed of

banking services;

- to ensure the wide use of information technologies in the operational activities of banks in order to increase the share of remote banking services" [2].

The regulation "On the requirements for managing the liquidity of commercial banks" establishes the following prudential standards for the liquidity of commercial banks:

1. **Current liquidity ratio.**

The current liquidity ratio is determined by the ratio of the sum of current assets (the bank's liquid assets and deposits with a maturity of up to 30 days, excluding overdue or overdue loans) to the sum of current liabilities (obligations that are due and payable within 30 days) and is 30 percent should not be less.

When determining the current liquidity ratio, deposits and loans placed or drawn on the interbank market for up to 30 days are net, if assets are greater than liabilities, the increased amount is included in current assets, if liabilities are greater than assets, the increased amount is included in current liabilities. In this case, the sum of assets and liabilities that is less is deducted from both current assets and current liabilities.

$$CLA = \text{Current Assets} / \text{Current Liabilities} * 100\% \geq 30\%$$

In this,

current assets - liquid assets and deposits of the bank with a payment term of up to 30 days, except for extended or overdue loans;

current obligations - obligations until demand and execution period up to 30 days.

2. **Current liquidity ratio.**

The current liquidity ratio is determined by the ratio of the amount of cash and other payment documents, securities of the Government of the Republic of

Uzbekistan and the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the bank's funds in the accounts of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (except for the funds in the mandatory reserve account of the Central Bank) to the amount of liabilities until demand.

When calculating the current liquidity ratio, only funds in the national currency of the Republic of Uzbekistan are taken into account.

Current liquidity ratio should not be less than 10 percent.

$$\text{LCR} = \frac{\text{Highly liquid assets}}{\text{Total net income for the next 30 days}} \times 100\% > 90\%$$

3. Liquidity coverage ratio

Liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) is defined as the ratio of highly liquid assets to total net outflow within the next 30 days (LCR =highly liquid assets/total net outflow within the next 30 days).

Inflow within the next 30 days and outflow within the next 30 days

In case of exceeding 75 percent, 75 percent of the output within the next 30 days will be taken as income within the next 30 days.

The coefficient of recalculation of inflows and outflows within the next 30 days is set by the Central Bank and depends on the type and duration of obligations.

LCR It should not be less than 100 percent. This indicator is 2019

From September 1:

in all currencies;

in national currency;

must be provided in foreign currencies (sum of all foreign currencies).

4. Net stable funding rate ratio

Available amount of sustainable financing/required amount of sustainable financing is defined as the ratio of the available amount of sustainable financing to

the required amount of sustainable financing (SBMMK=available amount of sustainable financing/required amount of sustainable financing).

SBMMK(available amount of sustainable financing/required amount of sustainable financing) should not be less than 100 percent. This indicator from September 1, 2019:

in all currencies;

in national currency;

must be provided in foreign currencies (sum of all foreign currencies).

SBMMK(available amount of sustainable financing/required amount of sustainable financing) to have stable sources of financing, taking into account the terms of return of assets, as well as

It is necessary to meet the demand for liquidity (required stable funding) by including liabilities in off-balance sheet items with a term of more than 1 year.

The available amount of sustainable financing includes:

total capital;

bank obligations with a valid repayment term of 1 year or more;

30 percent of the amount of other deposits and loan funds without a specified repayment period;

30% of the amount of other deposits and loan funds with a repayment term of less than 1 year.

The required amount of sustainable financing includes:

bank assets with a repayment period of 1 year or more, including problem loans and non-financial assets (land plots, buildings, furniture, computers and cars);

assets that are in litigation or have not been recovered in the prescribed manner;

30% of the amount of other assets with a repayment period of less than 1 year, excluding liquid assets with a repayment period of less than 1 year or with no

maturity;

15 percent of off-balance sheet items.

In this case, off-balance sheet items include unsecured documented letters of credit opened by a commercial bank, bank guarantees, options issued by a commercial bank, and forward contracts of the bank." [3].

According to the newly revised Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the Central Bank:

within the implementation of the monetary policy, the Central Bank determines the norms of mandatory reserves transferred by the banks to the depositors in the Central Bank under the obligations of the banks;

The Central Bank carries out operations on providing and withdrawing liquidity in the money market for the purposes of influencing the level of market interest rates, as well as maintaining and regulating the liquidity of the banking system;

in order to ensure the continuity of payments in the event of a temporary shortage of liquidity, the Central Bank has the right to provide quick assistance to commercial banks in the form of short-term loans for a period of up to three months in order to maintain liquidity. The interest rate on these loans should not be lower than the current rates on other loans of the Central Bank and it should be secured by the bank's assets. [4].

It should be recognized that the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 23, 2018 No. PQ-3620 "On additional measures to increase the popularity of banking services" has become important from the point of view of increasing the level of use of commercial bank loans by legal entities and individuals.

In accordance with this Decision, commercial banks:

study of advanced foreign banking experience and introduction of new types of banking services and products;

expanding the network of bank branches and mini-banks taking into account

the needs for banking services;

it was recommended to expand the rights of branches to make independent decisions without additional agreement with the main banks [5].

Five categories of classified loans based on the instructions of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the procedure for the classification of asset quality in commercial banks and the formation of reserves to cover possible losses on assets and the procedure for their use" (registered by the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan on July 14, 2015 with the number 2696) reserve allocations were formed for:

standard loans – 1%;

substandard loans – 10%;

unsatisfactory loans - 25%;

doubtful loans – 50%;

bad loans - 100%.

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